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Staff Development Programme And Entrepreneurship Job Performance In Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of staff development programme on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State. The objectives of the study were to: Determine the effect of employee training on entrepreneurship job performance. Ascertain the effect of employee orientation on entrepreneurship job performance. Examine the effect of career development on entrepreneurship job performance. The population of interest consists of all the employees staff of Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State. However the total Number of staff in the organization was 197. Given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research utilized the entire 197 population. The Method of data analysis was statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The researcher employed structure questionnaire as the method of data collection. Primary source of data was used. Percentage table and analysis of variance was used in this study. The study found that; Employee training has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State ($f=14.0$, $p.008$). Employee orientation has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State ($f=21.295$, $p.006$); Career development has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra State ($f=23.985$, $p.000$).It was recommended that Training programmes of the organization should be on a continuous basis and not based on survival, that is, conducting training only when the organization is confronted with particular problems. Since Employee orientation has a significant impact on employee development successful mentoring strategies are needed for the job that could offer considerable benefits to organizations and organizational managers.

Keywords: Employee training, Employee orientation. job performance, staff development programme

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The role of staffs in organizations is multifaceted. They are at the forefront in the organizational management and also constitute the lower levels workers and thus, staff development has therefore become the vehicle for meaningful change which plays an integral part in developing the organization's workforce. It is through promotion, training and development activities which differ in breadth in relation to the needs and resources of the organization, that professionalism, productivity, individual and organizational effectiveness and individual performance can be increased (Kaczynski, 2018).

Staff development as viewed by Okunade, (2020) is the core human resource management (HRM) function in organizations, and it is a process of expanding the knowledge, productivity, programmes that will enhance workers optimal performance. Human resource development is very fundamental in every organization and has to do with the education, skills levels, and problem solving abilities that will enable an individual to be a productive worker in the global economy of the 21st century. Staff development as a process is geared towards personal and professional growth of employees. It refers to the training whose aim is to improve and enhance personal knowledge, skills as well as attitudes. Organizations provide various staff development programmes to enable the employees to keep up with organizational challenges and innovations and to guarantee quality of service, productivity as well customer care (De Rijdt, Dochy, Bamelis, & Van der Vleuten, 2023).

The main objective of staff development is to improve and promote customer care, service delivery, and achievement of organizational goals as well as organizational competitiveness. The components of staff development include among others; orientation, skill training and continuing education. According to Yamoah (2023), when training is administered properly, it is likely to yield positive results with an increase level in performance. Induction training is key, as it introduces the employee to the organization in regards to the employment, the organizational policies and procedures, the remuneration packages and opportunities, position classification, promotion opportunities, job orientation as well as complaint procedures. Job orientation aims at guiding the individual employee towards the position he or she is hired for. The relationship between employee training and the quality of service delivered by employee to the customers is highly strong (Dhar, 2019) and the skills training is aimed at manual skills as well as communication skills.

Human resource is a critical and crucial resource besides the physical resources. However, in order to optimize this critical resource, it is the duty of the management to utilize effective staff development programmes. Studies indicate that employees and employers recognize the need and importance of staff development in enhancing job performance (Khan, Abbasi, Waseem, Ayaz, & Ijaz, 2016, Falola, Osibanjo, & Ojo, 2014, Onyango & Wanyoike, 2014). Despite the numerous benefits associated with staff development programmes, some institutions do not deem it necessary to provide the opportunity for employees to attain new skills and knowledge. This may be as a result of fear of the employee switching job after having expended in their training. Also is the problem of fund on the part of management to develop their staff.

While employee development is generally acknowledged to be crucial for employees to develop their knowledge, skills and attitudes, there are several challenges that tend to hinder their realization in organizations (Konings et al., 2019). Flynn et al. (2015), indicate that T&D strategies are sometimes not tailored to fit specific needs of employees, and therefore become irrelevant to them. They suggest that, for employee development to be to be effective, it needs to follow a systematic plan and be correctly implemented following all the steps of the process

previous analysis of training needs, development and implementation of an adequate training plan and evaluation. Other scholars have also found the lack of training expertise and support from management as other challenges.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine effect of staff development programme on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of employee training on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state.
2. Ascertain the effect of employee orientation on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state.
3. Examine the effect of career development on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Staff Development

Staff development as put by Afianmagbon and Nwokocha (2011) refers to all the programmes designed for the continuous improvement of skills and job performance of staff. It is also regarded as professional growth, and a genuine sense of learning, growing and developing of a person in his bid to contribute to the success of the establishment. Staff development Programme helps the individual to realize his potential for growth within the organization. It is important that recruited qualified staff be trained or given orientation to familiarize them with their basic job specification. Staff development refers to all policies, practices, and procedures used to develop the knowledge, skills, and competencies of in order staff to improve the effectiveness and efficiency both of the individual and the organization.

Staff development according to Armstrong (2012) can be seen as the most valuable and indispensable element of an organization. It is the pivot upon which all other resources, such as structures, finances, machines and facilities rely on to function. Pemida, (2017) opined that staff development refers to a variety of education and training activities which are designed purposely to give staff additional knowledge, skills, attitude, experiences and understanding needed to perform up to required standard.

The objectives of staff development programmes are to ensure the promotion of professional growth, improve in skills, keep employees abreast of new knowledge, meet particular work need and orientation, leadership responsibility, help new employees to adjust in organization and promote mutual respect among staff (Madumere-Obike, 2017). There is the need to ensure that the development programmes serve the expected purposes through the acquisition of the required knowledge and skills by the staff.

2.1.2 Entrepreneurship Job Performance

Entrepreneurship job performance of employees remains an issue of great concern to many organizations, including the school. Performance may be described as an act of accomplishing or executing a given task (Rafiq, et al, 2021). It can also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives (Kuncoro & Dardiri, 2017). Entrepreneurship job performance can be described as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Also, it is the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of the

teaching and learning process. According to Peretomode (2012), job performance is determined by the worker's level of participation in the day - to - day running of the organization.

Many organizations tend to spend huge sums of money on upgrading their plant and equipment yet little on upgrading their human capital. Teachers are an asset to the school. Without skill development, teachers' performance could be hampered. If the teachers do not receive on-going training, up to date equipment will not be used optimally. Employees who continuously upgrade their skill will also improve their productivity. The more skilled the workforce is, the easier it will be for the entire organization to adapt to changes that may arise in the organization.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on both the McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory.

McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory

This study is anchored on McClelland Achievement Motivation Theory as presented by McClelland in 1940. The theory postulates that people are motivated in varying degrees by their need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired, or learned, during an individual's lifetime. In other words, most people possess and will exhibit a combination of three needs. Achievement Motivation Theory attempts to explain and predict behavior and performance based on a person's need for achievement, power, and affiliation".

The Achievement Motivation Theory is also referred to as the Acquired Needs Theory or the Learned Needs Theory. The Acquired Needs Theory as McClelland theorized proposes that "certain types of needs (achievement, affiliation, power) are acquired during an individual's lifetime". The Achievement Motivation Theory evolved from work McClelland began in the 1940s. In 1958 McClelland described human motives in the Methods of Measuring Human Motivation. At that point, McClelland identified that human motives related to the achievement motive, the affiliation motive, and the power motive. McClelland focused his attention on only need for Achievement, the need for Affiliation, and the need for Power.

In essence, McClelland's theory postulates that people are motivated in varying degrees by their need for achievement need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired, or learned, during an individual's lifetime. In relation to this study, teachers can be motivated by the use of seminars, workshops, induction/orientation programmes, in-service training, etc. This will ensure effective discharging of their duties and in realization of education goals. Achievement is a goal that is desired, both the students, teachers and principals see it as a motivation to success. McClelland's idea explains and predicts behavior and performance based on a person's "need for achievement, power, and affiliation".

It is a goal which a teacher can set to achieve in their job in terms of their performance. With this theory, a teacher can predict his students learning outcome through various assessments carried out on them. The theory deems it fit to know the strength and weakness of the teachers and ways of making adjustment if need be. It can also be a good platform for teachers to improve in their job performance as well because people with high need for achievement want to take personal responsibility for solving problems, work at problems than leave the outcome to chance, they tend to take moderate risks rather than high or low risk, set moderate, realistic and attainable achievement tasks and are inclined to take calculated risks and they desire regular and concrete feedback on their performance which is very necessary for improvement. In relation to this study, teachers can be motivated by the use of seminar, workshop, induction/orientation programmes, in-service training etc. this will ensure effective discharging of their duties and realization of education goals. Achievement is a goal that is desired, both the students, teachers and principals see it as a motivation to success.

2.3. Empirical Review

Ogar and Nkanu, (2022) investigated staff development as a predictor of job performance of academic librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The main purpose was to assess the relationship between staff development and job performance of academic librarians in University libraries in South-South, Nigeria. Ex-post- facto research design was adopted. The population of the study comprises 175 academic librarians working in public university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The entire population was used for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. A total of 175 questionnaires were administered to the respondents and all were returned. Four (4) of the returned questionnaires were rejected because they were not completely filled. Therefore, a total of 171 questionnaires (98%) were used for the analysis. Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) were used to answer the research questions, Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis for the research questions show that, there is a relationship between staff development and job performance of academic librarians in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The results of the analysis also show that the hypothesis was rejected. This means that, there is a significant relationship between staff development and job performance of academic librarians in university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2025) The study analyzed the financial literacy and its impact on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. The objective of the study was to; ascertain the effect of financial knowledge, financial behaviour and financial expertise on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Three research hypotheses are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. The population of the study is made of youths from age 20-39 in South East zone of Nigeria, which is 50,222,32 target population. It comprises of all the youths in South East Nigeria, while the sample size is 399 were gotten through taro yamane formular. The researcher distributes three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires but only three hundred and seventy-three (373) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Correlation and t-test method of data analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study shows that; Financial knowledge has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Financial behaviour has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2025) examined the effect of artificial intelligent (AI) on decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT). A structure questionnaire was developed for data collection. The population of the study comprised of 281 management staff from thirteen (13) lubricant firms in Anambra State. Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) were duly filled and returned data was analysed using correlation analysis with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. Findings from the study show that. Machine learning has significant effect on decision support system on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=2.244$, $P=0.006$). Neural networks has significant effect on creative decision skill on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=9.790$, $P=0.009$). The study concludes that AI-powered predictive analytics improved decision-making in supply chain management in lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigerian..

Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi (2025) Investigated the digital cyberspace cost on firm performance of deposit money bank using data for the period of 2012-2023. Panel least squared (PLS) method

of data analysis was adopted because of its Best Linear Unbiased Estimators (BLUE) properties. The data for the variables used was sourced from annual report of the selected deposit money bank in Nigeria. The variables were on cyber security maintenance cost and cyber security acquisition cost. The study adopted the descriptive statistics, correlation approach, as well as panel least square. E- View software was used for the analysis. The study found that Cyber security maintenance cost has significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 3.491757, $p=0.0008$). Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 0.959399, $p=0.3405$).

Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, (2024) Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. while two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027. Material procurement has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 33.048. Logistic has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 9.418. Stock and waste control has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha.

Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, (2025) examined job satisfaction and employee's performance among the staff of private universities in Anambra state. The study investigated the relationship between reward, career development, staff training and recognition on employee performance. Relevant theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on Herzberg's theory. The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. The population of the study comprised 478 staff of private universities in Anambra state. Formulated hypothesis were tested, using ANOVA. From the analysis, it was discovered that: Reward has significant effect on employee's performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Career advancement has significant effect on employee's performance, amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state. Training has significant effect on employees' performance amongst the staff of private universities in Anambra state.

Atueyi, & Mbanefo (2025) examined the Igbo apprenticeship system and sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The objective of the study was to; Determine the impact of igba boi/odibo on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. Examine the effect of imu oruaka on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The study was anchored on cultural materialism theory. A structure questionnaire was developed for data collection. The population for the study comprised of business owners who have been in the business from 5 years upwards the study chose three markets from the three senatorial zones in Anambra state which are Nnewi Spare Parts Markets, (1,467) Onitsha Main Market, (1,545) and Eke Awka (1200). This gave a total of 4212 population, sample size of 809, was derived from Borg & Gall (1973) formular. Findings from the study show that. Igba boi/odibo has significant effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra State. Imu oruaka has significant effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra State. The study concludes that Igbo apprenticeship system has significant positive effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The study recommends that There should be more regulations in this scheme to provide adequate legal framework to guide and regulate the scheme. On the part of the masters

(Ogas), they should ensure that they teach the apprentice the required basic skills to excel in the business and also provide support and mentorship even after the apprenticeship period/training. Atueyi, & Mbanefo (2025) examined the Igbo apprenticeship system and sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The objective of the study was to; determine the impact of igba boi/odibo on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. Examine the effect of imu oruaka on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The study was anchored on cultural materialism theory. A structure questionnaire was developed for data collection. The population for the study comprised of business owners who have been in the business from 5 years upwards the study chose three markets from the three senatorial zones in Anambra state which are Nnewi Spare Parts Markets, (1,467) Onitsha Main Market, (1,545) and Eke Awka (1200). This gave a total of 4212 population, sample size of 809, was derived from Borg & Gall (1973) formular. Findings from the study show that. Igba boi/odibo has significant effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra State. Imu oruaka has significant effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra State. The study concludes that Igbo apprenticeship system has significant positive effect on sustainable economic development in Anambra state. The study recommends that There should be more regulations in this scheme to provide adequate legal framework to guide and regulate the scheme. On the part of the masters (Ogas), they should ensure that they teach the apprentice the required basic skills to excel in the business and also provide support and mentorship even after the apprenticeship period/training.

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The research design encompasses the methods for the collection, measurement and analysis of data related to the research objectives. The research design chosen for this study is survey method. The survey research method is most appropriate because the researcher has no control of the variables as well as the outcome.

3.2: Sources of Data

3.2.1 Primary Source

Primary data are firsthand or raw data, original records and materials created by participants or witnesses of the event(s) under study. In primary data for the study, personal interview and questionnaire will be used.

3.3: Population of the Study.

The population of interest consists of all the employees of staff of Eastern Plain Integrated Farm Igbariam. However the total Number of staff in that organization is 197. This population figure was derived from human resources department of the Obiano poultry farm Anambra State

3.4: Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research utilized the entire 197 population.

3.5 Instrument for data Collection.

The researcher made use of structure questionnaire divided into two sections. This was designed in such a way to obtain relevant information from the respondents. The first section is personal data of the respondents while the second section is the respondents' perception on the investigation of effect of employee development on employee performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farm Igbariam, Nigeria

3.6 Method of data analysis

Statistics, such as frequency count and percentages will be used in the analysis of personal characteristics, while hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents through the administered questionnaires. One hundred & ninety-seven questionnaires (197) were administered, among the staff of Eastern Plain Integrated Farm. However, one hundred and eighty-three (183) questionnaires were retrieved. Therefore the analysis and interpretation of data were only based on the returned questionnaires. The validity and reliability of this study is highly ensured, despite the number of questionnaires not returned.

4.1 Demographic characteristics of Respondent

4.1.1 Gender

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	63	34.4	34.4
	Female	120	65.6	100.0
	Total	183	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The above table reveals that the sixty-three (63) of the respondents which represents 34.4% were male respondents, while one hundred and twenty (120) respondents which represent 65.6% were female respondents. By implication, female respondents were more than male respondents by 31.2% in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.1.2 status

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	63	34.4	34.4
	Married	52	28.4	62.8
	Widowed	13	7.1	69.9
	Divorced	23	12.6	82.5
	Separated	32	17.5	100.0
	Total	183	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

In the table above, out of the one hundred and eighty-three (183) respondents, sixty-three (63) of the respondents are single. While fifty-two (52) respondents which represent 28.4 percent were married. Thirteen (13) of the respondents which represents 7.1 are widowed. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents are married as at the time of this study. Again, twenty-three (23) respondents which represent 12.6 percent were divorced. Lastly, thirty-two (32) respondents which represent 17.5 percent were separated. Thus, marital status table help us to know the number of single, married, and divorced respondents that answered the distributed questionnaire.

4.1.3 level of education

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	B.Sc/HND	96	52.5	7.7
	WAEC	66	36.1	43.7
	FSLC	14	7.7	96.2
	MSC	7	3.8	100.0
	Total	183	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

In the table above, out of the One hundred & ninety-seven (197) respondents, ninety-six (96) of the respondents are B.Sc/HND holders. While sixty-six (66) respondents which represent 36.1 percent are holders. Fourteen (14) respondents which represent 7.7 are FSLC holders, while seven (7) which represents 3.8 are M.Sc holders.

4.1.4 Age

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	111	60.7	60.7
	31-40	53	29.0	89.6
	41-50	10	5.5	95.1
	51-60	9	4.9	100.0
	Total	183	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The table above shows that respondents whose age bracket falls between 20-30 yrs were one hundred and eleven (111) which represent 60.7 percent. This is followed by those with age bracket of 31-40 years with fifty-three (53) which represents 29%. Also those within age bracket of 41-50yrs were ten (10) which represents 5.5%. Lastly, those with age bracket of 51-60 years with nine (9) which represents 4.9%. The implication of this age distribution is to enable us to check if the questionnaire was directed to the right age group.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

To further justify the results, ANOVA test was conducted to the effect of staff employee development on employee performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state, Nigeria. The results were shown in the ANOVA Table below;

Hypotheses one

Ho₁: Employee training has no significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1863344666.602	2	53238419.046	14.067	.008
Within Groups	397198.932	181	397198.932		
Total	1863741865.534	183			

Source: SPSS Version 20, 2025

The test table reveal that small significance value (F. sig<.05) indicate group differences. Since the F- value of 14.067 which has a significance of .008 is less than .05 (i.e .001<.05), there exist significant difference among the variables. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted, which states that Employee training has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Employee orientation has no significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18816621102816.1 95	2	537617745794.748	21.985	.000
Within Groups	64810152397.620	181	64810152397.620		
Total	18816621102816.1 95	183			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20 2025

The small significance value (F.sig<.05) indicates that there is a group difference. Since the F- value of 21.985 which has a significance value of .000 is less than .05 (i.e 000<.05). This implies rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of alternative hypothesis which state Employee orientation has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in eastern plain integrated farms, Igbariam, Anambra state

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Career development has no significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	881.762	2	25.193	15.385	.000
Within Groups	3.511	181	3.511		
Total	885.274	183			

Source: SPSS, Version, 20, 2025

The test conducted revealed that the large significance value (F.sig<.002) indicate no group differences. Since the F-value of 15.385 with a significance of .002 is less than .05 (i.e .002<.05).

Career development has significant effect on entrepreneurship job performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the staff development and employee performance in Eastern Plain Integrated Farms, Igbariam, Anambra state, Nigeria. The findings from the study unveils that significant and positive correlations exist between employee development and employee performance and organization performance. This implies that, when managers/administrators embark on effective development and development the dwindling performance of employees and poor organizational performance could be remedy. Hence, it becomes very important to devise a formidable strategy to eradicate the constraints that stand against human resource development to a halt. This study therefore suggests that, management of organizations should work with the strategic plan of the organization to ensure the judicious utilization of resources allocated for human capital training and development.

5.3 Recommendation

- i. Training programmes of the organization should be on a continuous basis and not based on survival, that is, conducting training only when the organization is confronted with particular problems
- ii. Since Employee orientation has a significant impact on employee development successful mentoring strategies are needed for the job that could offer considerable benefits to organizations and organizational managers
- iii. For effective and efficient employee performance, the farmer managers should consider combining Career development for greater organizational performance.

REFERENCES

- Afianrnagbon, B. E. & Mwokocha, L. K. (2011). Educational administration and management in Nigeria: The salient issues. Owerri: Solotech Press.
- Armstrong, M (2013). A Handbook of Human Resources management practices. UK: Kogan page, 986
- Atueyi, C. L. & Mbanefo P (2025). Igbo Apprenticeship System and Sustainable Economic Development in Anambra State. *journal of emerging trends in management sciences and entrepreneurship*, 7(1), 425-440.
- Dhar, R. L. (2019). Service quality and the training of employees: The mediating role of organizational commitment. *Tourism Management*, 46, 419-430.
- Falola, H. O., Osibanjo, A. O., & Ojo, S. I. (2014). Effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organisation competitiveness in the Nigerian banking industry. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V*, 7(1), 161.
- Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2024) Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling company Onitsha Anambra State. *International Journal of Economics, Finance & Entrepreneurship*, 9(8) 17-32
- Ifechukwu-Jacobs, C.J Arinze, E. S.; & Nwangwu, J.C & Atueyi, C.L (2025). Financial literacy and youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 13(2):152-162, April-June, 2025
- Khan, A. A., Abbasi, S. O. B. H., Waseem, R. M., Ayaz, M., & Ijaz, M. (2016). Impact of training and development of employees on employee performance through job satisfaction: A study
- Kuncoro, T., & Dardiri, A. (2017). Teacher Performance and work environment in instructiona process in vocational school. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5003526>
- Madumere-Obike, C. U. (2017). Refocusing teacher education for sustainable development: A case for continuous teacher development programmes. *Knowledge Review*, 15(7):1-6.

- Nwangwu, J.C, Ohanyere, C.P Nwangwu, U.C & Atueyi, C.L (2025). Artificial Intelligence (AI) and decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 13(1):242-254,
- Ogar, F. O. and Nkanu, W. O. (2022) Staff development as a predictor of job performance of academic librarians in University Libraries in South-South, Nigeria. *Journal of Library Services and Technologies*, 4(1), 29 - 42
- Ohanyere C. P., Arinze, S.E. & Atueyi C. L. (2025). Digital cyberspace cost and performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 13(3):168-176,
- Onya, C. C.; Dr Arinze, S. E.& & Atueyi, C.L (2025) Job satisfaction and employee performance in private universities In Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research* 13(2):229-241,
- Onyango, J. W., & Wanyoike, D. M. (2014). Effects of training on employee performance: a survey of health workers in Siaya County, Kenya. *European Journal of Material Sciences*, 1(1), 11-15.
- Pemida, R.O. (2017). An investigation into the recruitment and retention of teachers in Kogi State primary schools. Unpublished master these. ABU, Zaria
- Peretomode, V.F. (2012). *Theories of Management Implication for Educational Administrators*. Benin: Justice Jeco Printing Publishing Global.
- Rafiq, M., Ghaffar, A. & Zaman, A. (2021). Impact of Teachers Social Capital on their performance a narrative inquiry. *Liberal Arts and Social Sciences International Journal*, 5(1), 1-15.<https://doi.org/10.47264/ideal.lassij/5.1.1>
- Yamoah, E. E. (2023). Employee training and empowerment: A conceptual model for achieving high job performance. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(13), 27-30.